

A Phenomenology Study on Primary School First, Second, and Third Grade Teachers' Perceptions About Root Value and Value Concept in Life Sciences Lesson and towards Root Value and Value Teaching

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Abstract

The research, which aims to reveal the perceptions of primary school first, second and third grade teachers about the concept of root value and value and teaching of root values and values, was carried out in a primary school in the Dilovası district of Kocaeli province in the 2017-2018 academic year. Phenomenology was used as the research design. Six participants, two male and four female, participated in the study as participants. Semi-structured interview form and observation method were used to obtain the data of the research. In the process of analyzing the data, the interviews were audio recorded and then transcribed in the computer environment, and the data were analyzed with the content analysis method. According to the data obtained, it has been observed that the teachers do not have sufficient knowledge about root values, the methods, techniques, activities and evaluation activities used in teaching root values or values. It has been seen that the course content and the course book are not at the desired level in the teaching of root values and values. It has been concluded that teachers have deficiencies in the subject of root value or value teaching.

Limitedness

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of the world literature and data. The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Restricted by literature review.

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Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to realize these principles in the field of related sciences.

Abstract

The research, which aims to reveal the perceptions of primary school first, second and third grade teachers about the concept of root value and value and teaching of root values and values, was carried out in a primary school in the Dilovası district of Kocaeli province in the 2017-2018 academic year. Phenomenology was used as the research design. Six participants, two male and four female, participated in the study as participants. Semi-structured interview form and observation method were used to obtain the data of the research. In the process of analyzing the data, the interviews were audio recorded and then transcribed in the computer environment, and the data were analyzed with the content analysis method. According to the data obtained, it has been observed that the teachers do not have sufficient knowledge about root values, the methods, techniques, activities and evaluation activities used in teaching root values or values. It has been seen that the course content and the course book are not at the desired level in the teaching of root values and values. It has been concluded that teachers have deficiencies in the subject of root value or value teaching

Keywords: *Root values, value, Life Studies, value teaching*

The survival of a community or a society in general, the shaping of its future depends on raising people who have gained the values existing in a large part of the society and can apply these values in daily life (Cited by Yaşaroğlu, 2018).

The concept of value is the moral rules, goals, ways of thinking or belief styles that are accepted by the majority of the society or participate in the social community that ensures the continuity of any social community or society as a whole. Values are considered by societies to be useful to them. The concept of value is not only about knowing or consciousness, but also various emotions are included in the concept of value. Values play a role in the formation of the behaviors of individuals or in the shaping of the behaviors of individuals and in the process of realizing the behaviors by the individual (Cited by Demir and İşcan 2007).

The concept of root value is also included in the Life Studies course curriculum, which was changed in 2017. Some root values have been determined in the curriculum. These root values can be given as values on their own and can be considered together with other values to which they are associated. Ten root values were determined in the curriculum. These root values are: justice, benevolence, patriotism, friendship, honesty, responsibility, love, respect, self-control and patience (MEB, 2018)

Raising or creating a society that has internalized root values or values is among the basic duties of schools. The behaviors and approaches of schools in this process have a significant impact on the behavior and value understanding of future generations. If the aimed values are acquired in the school, it can be ensured that the society gains the targeted values. Value education enables the elimination of negative and undesirable values in individuals. In values education, the program and values should not be considered separately from each other, and values should be included in the program (cited in Yaşaroğlu, 2018).

Considering that the textbook and the content of the program are used in value teaching, field experts have important duties in this process. Field experts should use an appropriate book and content creation process for the individual to gain a positive value in the book and content

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creation process. In the process of realizing these, field experts should ensure that various stories or case studies are included in the books. Field experts should be able to critically look at the textbooks on value teaching and intervene in the parts that are missing or need to be corrected. The course books should include activities or studies that enable the student to be active and perform various tasks. Textbooks should be prepared in such a way that the student can make choices, make judgments and compare in the process of gaining value (Demir & İşcan, 2007).

Methodological

When we look at the research design used in this study, the phenomenology design, one of the qualitative research designs, was used. The phenomenology design appears as a qualitative research design that allows focusing on the phenomena that are aware of but lacking a deep and detailed knowledge and understanding, in which the phenomenon is tried to be understood in depth, the phenomenon is examined in detail, and it provides the opportunity to go to the essence of the phenomenon (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016; cited in Ozkan, 2017).

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The study group of the study consists of six classroom teachers who gave education in a state primary school in the Dilovası district of Kocaeli province in 2017-2018. While transferring the research data, the teachers were named as S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, and S6. Two of the six classroom teachers are male and four are female. Since phenomenological studies usually require long and multiple interviews, the sample size should not exceed 10 (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). In the selection method of the sample, the easily accessible case sampling method, which is one of the purposive sampling methods, was used. Purposive sampling method can be preferred because people who will be data sources in phenomenological studies should have experiences related to the phenomenon to be researched (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). Since easily accessible case sampling adds speed and practicality to the research, it may be preferable to use this type of sampling method (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016).

Two types of data collection methods were used in the study. The first of these is the interview method and the second is the observation method. When we look at the main data collection tool used in phenomenological studies, we see that the observation method is used (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). The tool used in the interview method is the semi-structured interview form developed by the researcher. In the process of creating the semi-structured interview form, the opinion of the qualitative research field expert was taken. As a result of the opinions received, the semi-structured interview form consisting of fifteen open-ended questions was given its final form. The second data collection method is the observation method. Observation is one of the data collection tools used in terms of both supporting and forming the basis for the interviews conducted in phenomenological studies (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). The course process, which was observed during the observation process, was noted by the researcher.

In the process of collecting the data, first of all, a semi-structured interview form, which is one of the data collection tools and created by the researcher, was used. The data were collected in May in the 2017-2018 academic year. The semi-structured interview form created by the researcher was applied to 6 classroom teachers. The interviews made by the researcher with the classroom teachers were recorded on a voice recorder with the permission of the classroom teachers. Interviews were held during lunch breaks and in the school library. The reason why the

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library was chosen to collect the data is that it is quiet, allowing audio recording and a healthier conduct of the interview. The second method used in the data collection process is the observation method. In the observation method, the process of teaching the Life Sciences course of a second grade and third grade teacher was observed for one hour and the observation process was recorded by taking notes by the researcher. In the study, content analysis method was used in the analysis of the data. The aim of the method in content analysis is to reach the expressions, concepts and themes from the obtained data. In the content analysis process, firstly, the data is coded, certain categories are created from the coded data, and themes are reached from the created categories, and finally, the themes reached, namely the findings, are interpreted (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). Content analysis method is a method that can be preferred in the analysis of data, since it is a question of revealing experiences and meanings in data analysis in phenomenological studies (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). The interviews of the samples participating in the study, which were recorded on the voice recorder, were transcribed in the computer environment and the data were analyzed after they were transcribed. During the analysis of the data, direct quotations about the participants of the study were also included.

From the literature

Teachers, who undertake one of the biggest tasks in value teaching, should set an example for students in order to ensure that students gain values, and it should be ensured that the expressions that will support the implementation of values are expressed by the teachers. Storytelling about values can be provided by teachers in the process. Students can be asked questions about values and the answers can be obtained. In order to ensure that values are seen in different environments, movie and theater watching activities can be organized or students can be offered suggestions in this way. Students can experience the process by enabling them to take part in various social responsibility projects or various studies related to the values they have learned or internalized. In this process, students can be given case studies and asked to interpret them. In value teaching, studies and activities in which students are active and actively participate should be used frequently. It is possible to help students internalize values by providing animation activities by teachers. Values education can be carried out of school by giving the lives of various people as research assignments (Kurtdere Fidan, 2009).

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In value teaching, besides individual activities and studies, group studies and activities can be included. Drama method can be used. Activities that will enable students to learn by doing and experiencing can be included. In value teaching, more than one method can be used instead of using a single method in the lessons so that teachers can have a more effective and productive lesson process (Meydan & Bahçe, 2010).

Value teaching is not just a process done at school. Values education can be continued outside of school, and the family has the most responsibility in this process. Making the value given by the teacher in the school negative in the family can cause a negative effect in the process of gaining the values (Kurtdere Fidan, 2009). In the process of gaining values, not only the school and family are effective, but also the environment of the individual is effective in this process. For this, it is necessary to be in constant communication with both parents and the environment, and seminars, conferences, informative meetings should be organized in order for them to be informed correctly (Meydan and Bahçe, 2010).

People who are negative role models of media and technology in value education, and the fact that knowledge is mostly in the foreground in lessons has a negative effect on value teaching (Fidan, 2009; Meydan ve Bahçe, 2010).

Various trainings should be given to teachers on value education and teachers should be informed about this issue (Kurtdere Fidan, 2009).

Rationale of the Study

The research has two general aims. The first aim of the study is to investigate how the root values and values in the Life Studies curriculum are perceived by primary school first, second and third grade teachers. The second aim of the study is to investigate the process of teaching the root values and values in the Life Studies curriculum by primary school first, second and third grade teachers

Results

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Two data collection tools were used in the study. The first is interview and the second is observation. In the findings section of the study, firstly, the findings obtained from the interview method are included. Secondly, the findings obtained from the observation are included.

Findings Obtained from Interviews with Teachers

A semi-structured interview form was used in the interviews with the teachers. While presenting the findings, it was made according to the question titles used in the semi-structured interview form and the findings were conveyed.

1. Which grades do you teach?

Table 1. Classes Taught by Teachers

Class(Code and Theme)	Number
First class	2
Second class	2
third grade	2

As seen in Table 1, 2 of the primary school teachers participating in the research are first grade teachers, 2 are second grade teachers, and 2 are third grade teachers.

2. How many years have you been teaching?

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Table 2.1. Number of Years Teachers Have Been Teaching

Year Instructed (Code)	Number
2	1
4,5	1
15	1
16	1
19	1
20	1

Table 2.2. Number of Years Teachers Have Been Teaching

Year of Teaching (Theme)	Number
0-5	2
11-15	1
16-20	3

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Table 2.2.' As can be seen, it is understood that 2 teachers have been teaching for 0-5 years, 1 teacher has been teaching for 11-15 years, and 3 teachers have been teaching for 16-20 years. Table 2.2. As we can see from.

3. What does the concept of "value" mean to you?

Table 3.1. Expression of the Concept of Value in Teachers (Codes)

S1	Moral concepts, the things we care about, the processes that guide our lives
S2	Considered behaviors
Ö3	learning to learn
Ö4	Morality
Ö5	Human characteristics
Ö6	The important thing is concepts that make life easier

Table 3.2. Expression of the Concept of Value in Teachers

Themes	Number
things that matter	3

Morality	2
The process that drives our lives	1
Concept that makes our life easier	1
Human characteristics	1
learning to learn	1

As we can see in Table 3.2., from the answers given by the teachers to the question of what the concept of value means for them, it is understood that three people emphasized the important things and two emphasized the moral theme. Below are the statements made by teachers named S4 and Ö6:

S4: "The first word that comes to mind when I think of the concept of value is morality. In other words, it is important for me that children be more ethical than academic success."

S6: "I think it is an important thing for students to earn. I think sitting and standing up as concepts that will make life easier. Love and respect are the main things that are important in their life."

4. In your opinion, what are the values that should definitely be taught to students?

Table 4.1. Values to be Gained to Students (Codes)

S1	Love, respect, understanding, empathy, family
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S2 Respect for elders, patriotism, patriotism

Ö3 Conscientious values, respect, love, tolerance

Ö4 Don't lie, don't steal

Ö5 Love, respect, tolerance, understanding, peace

Ö6 Knowing how to speak, tolerance, love, respect, self-expression, self-management

Table 4.2. Values to be Gained to Students

Themes	Number
Love	6
Respect	5
Tolerance	3

Being savvy	1
Empathy	1
Family	1
conscientious values	1
not to lie	1
not to steal	1
Peace	1
Knowing how to speak and express yourself	1
Self-management of your life	1

As seen in Table 4.2., 6 people emphasized the value of love, 5 people emphasized the value of respect and 3 people emphasized the value of tolerance to the question of what values should be taught to students. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö5 and Ö6:

S5: "These are the most important values that we need to bring in; love, respect, tolerance, understanding and peace."

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S6: "Every student should learn how to speak, tolerance, love, respect, self-expression, and self-management."

5. What do you think "root value" means?

Table 5.1. Meaning of Root Value (Codes)

Ö1	Values conveyed by the family
Ö2	I have no clear information
Ö3	Values that make up the basic branches of education
Ö4	I don't know root value
Ö5	Main value, first value
Ö6	Values for self-management

Table 5.2. Meaning of Root Value

Themes	Number
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No answer	2
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Values conveyed by the family	1
-------------------------------	---

Values that make up the basic branches of education	1
---	---

Main value, first value	1
-------------------------	---

Values for self-management	1
----------------------------	---

As seen in Table 5.2., two teachers did not express an opinion on the question of what the root value means for you. One person expressed the values conveyed by the family, another person the values that form the basic branches of education, another person the main value, the value that should be at the top, and the values that he can manage his life by himself. Using the explanations and the answers given, it is seen that the teachers could not explain the meaning of the root value as desired and expressed. For this reason, a brief explanation was made by the researcher regarding the root value. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö2 and Ö3:

S2: *"Root value, root value. I do not have a clear information." Let me give you brief information, the latest changes were made in the programs, or all such Mathematics, Turkish and ten common values were determined. The root value is ten. "I didn't examine it."*

S3: *"What is the root value here?" The program has changed, or ten root values have been determined in all programs in primary education. These are the root values as common. "What are they?" Here I will ask you about them. "Well, I have no idea about these root values." I'm*

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going to ask you to guess. What could be the root value? Even if you think so, even if you don't know? "These are the values that make up the main branches of education. Are they talking about love, respect, tolerance and how to behave here?" There are exactly ten that we call the root value, and love and respect come into play. Values like these.

6. What are the root values in the Life Studies curriculum?

Table 6.1. Root Values Said by Teachers (Codes)

Ö1 Relationships, doing nothing without thinking

Ö2 respect for elders

Things that teach how to behave in society, environmental awareness, traffic rules, rules of behavior on the street, at home, at school and at dinner, love, respect, tolerance, rules that should and should not be done to people.

Ö3

Honesty, not lying, respecting the rights of the people, not stealing, respect for elders, love for the little ones, helping, sharing, solidarity

Ö4

Animal love, human love, values of all kinds of love, respect, respect for human values, peace, tolerance, values of friendship, freedom, perspective

Ö5

Ö6 Tolerance, love, respect, scientific

Table 6.2. Root Values That Teachers Say

Themes	Number
Respect	6
Love	5
Tolerance	3
Rules	3
Honesty	2
Relationships	1
do nothing without thinking	1
environmental awareness	1

Observing the copyright	1
not stealing	1
Help	1
Sharing	1
Solidarity	1
Peace	1
Friendship	1
Freedom	1
Opinion	1
scientificity	1

As seen in Table 6.2., when the teachers were asked what the root values could be, 6 people were given the answer of respect, 5 of them love, 3 of them tolerance, 3 of them rules, and 2 of them honesty. If we comment on the answers given by the teachers, it is seen that the teachers mentioned 4 of the 10 root values: These are; honesty, love, respect, helpfulness. The teachers did

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not mention the values of justice, friendship, self-control, patience, responsibility and patriotism. In the fifth question, sufficient and desired answers could not be received from the teachers about what the root value is. In this question, adequate and desired answers could not be obtained. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö3 and Ö6:

Ö3: *"The root values may be related to other behaviors. There are things that teach behavior, that is, how to behave in society. There are other issues related to environmental awareness, but there are other traffic rules related to everything else. Here are the rules about how to behave on the street. There are rules about eating at home, school or how to behave at dinner, love, respect, tolerance and all the rules that people should and should not do."*

Ö6: *"Either tolerance, love, respect, being scientific, I could remember many other things after that, but I can't think of them right now."*

7. What other values can be added to the root values in the Life Studies curriculum?

Table 7.1. Values that can be added to Root Values (Codes)

Ö1 Love, respect, tolerance, understanding each other

Ö2 Protecting animals, respecting their environment, respecting their elders, respecting the flag, respecting the National Anthem

Ö3 Capturing the pace of society, modernity

Ö4 Spiritual values, religion of Islam

Ö5 Freedom, respect, acceptance of others

Ö6 Putting yourself in someone else's place, valuing people, valuing animals, environmental awareness, being human

Table 7.2. Values that can be added to Root Values

Themes	Number
Respect	6
Empathy	2
valuing people	2
valuing animals	2
Love	1
Tolerance	1
Capture the pace of society	1

Modernity	1
spiritual values	1
Islamic religion	1
Freedom	1
environmental awareness	1
Being human	1

As seen in Table 7.2., 6 of the teachers said the value of respect, 2 of them empathy, 2 of them valuing people, and 2 of them valuing animals when asked what other values would you add to the root values. Among the values that teachers say, respect and love values are among the existing root values and teachers gave these values as examples to the values that can be added. This situation may lead to the interpretation that teachers do not know the root values sufficiently and at the desired level. Other values said by teachers; tolerance, catching the pace of society, modernity, spiritual values, religion of Islam, freedom, environmental awareness and being human. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö1 and Ö2:

Ö1: "Well, when I think about the value I would like to add, I mean, love, respect, tolerance are classics, or understanding each other apart from that."

Ö2: "I don't know as root value." By value. "Here, he protects animals, respects his environment, respects his elders, the flag, the National Anthem, they put these at the top, as the root value."

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8.1. Which methods, techniques and activities do you think should be used in the process of gaining the root values or values in the Life Studies curriculum, and which ones do you use?

Table 8.1. Using Methods, Techniques and Efficiency in Gaining Root Values and Values (Codes)

Ö1 Empathy, telling, giving examples, drama

Ö2 Practice by doing, slide show, enlighten parents

Ö3 Empathy, watching videos, reading stories, parent interviews, song teaching

Ö4 Learning by doing

Ö5 Drama, animation, question and answer

Ö6 Self-expression, question-answer, six-hats thinking, what would you do if it were you?

Table 8.2. Using Methods, Techniques and Efficiency in Gaining Root Values and Values

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Themes	Number
Empathy	3
Drama	2
Teaching by doing	2
Parent interviews	2
Question answer	2
Expression	1
giving an example	1
slideshow	1
video playback	1
story reading	1

song teaching	1
<hr/>	
Animation	1
<hr/>	
Enabling self-expression	1
<hr/>	
thinking with six hats	1
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As can be seen in Table 8.2., 3 teachers answered empathy, 2 persons drama, 2 persons teaching by doing, 2 persons parent interviews, 2 persons question-answer to the question of which methods, techniques and activities they use in the process of gaining root values and values. . The type of activity said by the teachers is 14 in total and the total number of activities by the teachers is 20. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö1 and Ö5:

Ö1: *"Well, we generally try to teach by telling. We try to make him empathize with his friend. We give examples. We explain them with the drama method and so on. In other words, there are various examples for them to understand about animals, not to harm animals, to add the value of love that they are also living things. That they need us. We try to do it by telling.*

Ö5: *"Drama method in general. Enacting an event. Question and answer."*

9. Which assessment activities do you think should be used and which ones do you use to evaluate whether the core values in the Life Studies curriculum are acquired by the students?

Table 9.1. Evaluation Activities for Root Values and Whether Values Have Been Acquired (Codes)

-
- Ö1 Observation
-
- Ö2 Observation, gain evaluation
-
- Ö3 Behavior assessment, observational look, scoreboard
-
- Ö4 Observation in their natural environment, visiting parents
-
- Ö5 True-false test, open-ended question, question-answer
-
- Ö6 Example case, what would you do if it were you?
-

Table 9.2. Evaluation Activities Regarding Root Values and Whether Values Have Been Acquired

Themes	Number
Observation	4
Question answer	2

Case study	1
parent visit	1
true-false test	1
gain evaluation	1
Behavior evaluation	1
scoreboard table	1
open-ended question	1

As can be seen in Table 9.2., to the question of which assessment activities are used by students to evaluate whether or not the root values and values are acquired, 4 teachers answered observation, 2 people question-answer, 1 person case study, 1 parent visit and one person true-false test. has given. The type of evaluation activity that the teachers answered was 9 and the total number of evaluation activities that the teachers said was 13. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö1 and Ö4:

Ö1: "The student already shows him in the classroom. We don't do exams and so on for this. I can observe changes in his behavior in the classroom. This is also observed in some students. Here is the child's attitude towards me, his respect for me, his love for me can change over time, they always gain value or are related to animals. I'm throwing it away, there are friends who treat

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animals badly by saying that I warned it and so on, I understand that this value has been earned, that is, love, love for living things, that sensitivity is gained, I observe the changes."

Ö4: "I prefer to observe them in their natural environment to see if they won or not. Parent visits are very important for me. That is, I will see the child I am going to in the family environment. I will observe him in the schoolyard without being noticed. I can follow him behind him. So the best thing to do in the natural environment is to detect it. Because I think what a child or adult individual will do when you enter the classroom environment, try to show you a slightly secondary face."

10. What are your views on whether the content of the Life Sciences course is sufficient to gain root values or values?

Table 10.1. Content of Life Sciences Lesson (Codes)

Ö1	Seems not enough to me
Ö2	enough on the subject
Ö3	Not as a subject
Ö4	very poor lesson
Ö5	I don't think it's enough
Ö6	I think it's a little shallower

Table 10.2. Content of Life Sciences Lesson

Themes	Number
Not enough	4
Sufficient	2

As can be seen in Table 10.2., to the question of whether the Life Studies textbook is sufficient for teachers to gain basic values and values, 4 of the teachers gave the answer not enough, 2 of them gave the answer enough. Teachers also made suggestions about how the content could be improved or how the Life Studies course should be done. These suggestions are as follows: More value should be included in the book, the family should give sufficient support to the student, the content should be made a little more concrete for the child, the content should be taught with concrete concepts and by doing-experience, the content can be taught by doing-experiencing or by making the theater watch, more details are included in the content. can be given, the content can include the case study and questions about the case study. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö2 and Ö5:

Ö2: "So. It is sufficient as a subject. But children have problems with children. There are serious problems. Therefore, I do not think that the curriculum is very deficient. So the curriculum did not do anything excessively, it did not change. It is suitable for the current level, but the family's interest in children does not support this. Because the child is constantly in possession of a phone, computer, there is no parental control. Here, fathers usually work from morning to evening. Mothers are also insufficient in the hands of mothers. Also, depending on the environment you live in, the child gets what the family sees, so it is an acquired one. It's very difficult to change things. So I think there's nothing wrong with a program."

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Ö5: "I don't think it's enough. Because values are gained by living a little bit. That's why our education system can't provide this environment. That's why I don't find it enough if these opportunities are provided by making them live, or children can watch the theater."

11. What are your views on whether the Life Studies textbook is sufficient for basic values or for gaining them?

Table 11.1. Life Sciences Textbook (Codes)

Ö1 Many topics have been taken, but as I said, these are not fully covered.

Ö2 No. Textbooks are not sufficient in general

Ö3 As a book, I think it's a bit lacking.

Ö4 The book is completely inadequate for me.

Ö5 Is it enough, of course, it can become more equipped

Ö6 Not enough

Table 11.2 Life Studies Textbook

Themes	Number
--------	--------

Not enough

6

As can be seen in Table 11.2., when asked to the teachers, whether the Life Studies textbook is sufficient to gain the basic values or values, all of the teachers answered that it is not sufficient. In addition, while answering this question, the teachers made some suggestions for the book to reach the desired level. These suggestions are as follows: In the books, something that can be empathic can be added, more subject narration can be included in the books, the study and the textbook can be harmonized with each other, they can be embodied in a way that the child can understand better, storytelling can be used, practice-oriented studies can be included instead of books, visuals can be emphasized. can be given, a narrative can be made according to the level of the child, concept teaching can be included, painting and puzzle activities can be included. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö2 and Ö4:

S2: *"No. Textbooks are generally not sufficient. Because, for example, there is only an application that gave the subject. You know, if they explained the subject once, you would tell them, the old books used to explain the subject, then the activity would be done. Now a child says that you guide us so that they find the subject. "Well, it will take me a week to do that, so it will take me a week to find something. Let it be explained first, even if it is short, small footnotes should be given in the book. According to him, the learning outcome should be evaluated accordingly. There is always an assessment. In other words, there is no lecture. There is a need for a lecture."*

S4: *"The book is completely inadequate for me. I say that I will say the same thing persistently and insistently, I do not know whether it is relevant or not, but the lack of physical areas in schools affects many lessons as a disadvantage or we cannot teach the lesson. What can I do in the Life Science lesson? They will give me a field. "I'm going to improvise on that area a little bit more. The classrooms are insufficient, and the crowded classrooms are a disadvantage for us. You will give me an empty classroom, and I will teach the life science lesson very well with the improvisation method. I think it is permanent."*

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12. What are your views on whether students gain root values or values?

Table 12.1. Whether Students Gain Root Values or Values (Codes)

Ö1 Seventy percent of those who have gained the core values are well past that.

Ö2 So it wins but it's heavy

Ö3 I mean, they win over time, but there are also those who can't.

Ö4 I don't think they won

Ö5 Overall I think it wins.

Ö6 Winners win, but for example, I notice that there is no change in some of them, so those who want to buy buy.

Table 12.2. Students' Root Values or Whether They Gain Values or Not

Themes	Number
they are winning	5

they can't win

1

Table 12.2. As can be seen in , the questions asked to the teachers about whether the students gain the root values or the values gave the answer that 5 of the teachers win, and 1 answer that they cannot. Some of the teachers also made some suggestions for students to gain root values or values. These suggestions are as follows: The family should also participate in the process, the teacher-parent-student should act together, and parent seminars should be organized. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö3 and Ö4:

Ö3: *"So they gain over time, but as I said, if there is no authority figure, there are also students who have serious problems in the transformation phase of their behavior, that is, in the education phase, but I think it is their families who feed them rather than whether they can learn something here. You know, education in their families, that is, education is now multi-legged. In the past, only teachers. here, school, parent, student consisted of three legs. I think that this education has too many legs. Therefore, things change after leaving here. I see that some students improve very seriously, they really gain these values and act accordingly. Not only outside of school, but also in many of them, I see that you are stubborn about not learning."*

Ö4: *"I don't think they won. Because no matter how much money I spend on myself at school, their main role models are their parents. Now I teach here, I teach, the child does some things very well, you describe it as very perfect, let him go home, and after a week there is no trace of him. Because adults in the house, he "The children at home will not practice the same behavior. The child will question himself this time, wondering if I am weird, why am I trying to do this behavior. That's why I think that the concept of teacher-parent-student should act together in education. We want parent seminars if possible."*

13. What do you think are the reasons why students cannot acquire root values or values?

Table 13.1. Reasons for Students Not Gaining Root Values or Values (Codes)

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Ö1 The environment, family, families are not conscious about raising children, the number of siblings is too many, they have financial difficulties, they grow up seeing bad examples, families do not fall on their children too much

Ö2 Reversing the work we do here at home, The family does not support us, now I say here, shut up, they use other ways to keep quiet

Ö3 The family does not direct the child correctly outside of school, spends much more time with technological devices, happens in environments where children should not be, not directing the child in the name of education.

Ö4 Family

Ö5 Family, social learning in the family, the people he takes as an example, influences the environment, he learns at school, he cannot apply what he learned at school, that is, the education at school does not continue at home

Ö6 I see trouble in the five-year-old group

Table 13.2. Reasons for Students Not Acquiring Root Values or Values

Themes	Number
Family	5
Environment	3
role models	2
Number of siblings	1
Economic Reasons	1
Technological tools	1
Age	1

As can be seen in Table 13.2., to the question asked to the teachers about the root values or the reasons why the students could not acquire the values, 5 of the teachers answered family, 3 people were the environment, 2 people were role models. Teachers stated 7 different reasons in response to this question, and the total number of stated reasons is 14. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö1 and Ö5:

Ö1: "As I said, the reasons for not being able to win are the environment, the family. Families are not very conscious about raising children because of the well-known environment. The number of siblings is too many. They have financial difficulties. Therefore, children grow up

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on the street and these children see other bad examples on the street. Children who do not go to school are affected by this negative situation because they use various drugs, cigarettes, alcohol, etc. also."

Ö5: "The biggest reason is the family. The social learning in the family. The people he takes as an example. These are the reasons. Otherwise, the essence of the children is all very clean, but they affect the environment. That's why I think they can't win. He learns at school, cannot apply what he learned at school at home. He encounters something different at home and then learns at school. he forgets this value. So education at school does not continue at home."

14. Who has a role in the process of gaining the students' root values or values?

Table 14.1. Those Who Have a Duty to Make Students Gain Root Values or Values (Codes)

Ö1 The family has a duty, the teacher

Ö2 Mother, father, school, environment are also important

Ö3 Well, parents are important, teacher, friend, person with behavior, market, grocery store, neighbor, the whole society.

Ö4 Teacher, mother and father, grandmother, grandfather, child himself

Ö5 family, environment, school

Ö6 Psychologist, pedagogue, people who are competent in education, school administration, family, parents

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Table 14.2. Those Who Have a Duty to Provide Students with Root Values

or Values

Themes	Number
Family	6
Environment	6
Teacher	3
School	2
whole society	1
the child himself	1
Psychologist	1
Educationalist	1
Relevant field experts	1
school administration	1

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As can be seen in Table 14.2., all of the teachers gave the answer of family, all teachers from the environment, 3 people as teachers, 2 people for school to the question asked to teachers, who is responsible for gaining the root values or values. In response to this question, teachers gave 10 different answers and a total of 23 answers. In addition to their answers to the question, some of the teachers also made suggestions about what kind of duties they should do: These suggestions are: family awareness should be raised, parent training should be given, awareness should not be limited to only teachers and parents, the whole environment should be conscious, the child should be educated on spiritual values, the family should be educated. education should continue at home, social life and education at school should be harmonized, school boards should be arranged, and teaching should be done with games.

Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö3 and Ö6:

Ö3: *"Everyone falls into the process. I think even this neighbor has a role in the process. He says who has a responsibility in the process of gaining students' fundamental values, not only parents, but maybe a friend who is older than himself or maybe a little friend, that is, the one who has taken the behavior. "Another person who has received education, or maybe sometimes a neighbor or a grocery store or grocery store, has a responsibility. I think the whole society has a responsibility."*

Ö6: *"For example, there may be psychologists, pedagogues, there may be people who are authorized in education. There may be parents outside of school. For example, as a root value, activities can be organized in the hall, for example during breaks, in places where first graders are located, boards can be organized, if facilities are used together with administrators, even Things can be done about them that they can play even while playing hopscotch. It can be gained in this way. It can be made into a game, and gaining those values. I think both children will not be idle during recess and we can prevent behavioral disorders in this way. Of course. The family has a responsibility in the first place. The biggest problem here is they come from the family as completely zero anyway. That's why it's a little late. Actually, these are things that should be given before. When you don't take it from the family, it seems very abstract here to the child. That's why sometimes it fails. Actually, seminars can be organized with families in the first place. Seminars*

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can be given by people who are more authorized on this subject than we can give. I don't know how effective it will be, though."

15. How would you evaluate yourself on the teaching of root values or values?

Table 15.1. Teachers' Views on themselves in Teaching Root Value or Value (Codes)

Ö1	I won't say I'm enough
Ö2	I believe I did my job well
Ö3	There are definitely flaws, but I think I'm good overall.
Ö4	I find successful
Ö5	As a realist, I think I have some shortcomings.
Ö6	I think it's missing

Table 15.2. Teachers' Views on themselves in the Teaching of Root Values or Values

Themes	Number
I have shortcomings	3

As it is seen in Table 15.2., when we look at the answers of the teachers about how the teachers evaluate themselves in the teaching of root values or values, 3 people answered that I have deficiencies and 3 people answered that I am successful. Teachers also expressed various reasons why they had deficiencies: These reasons are as follows: Environment, behavioral disorders of students, time, values for lower classes being abstract, not sending every student to kindergarten, reading level of parents, low literacy rate, inadequacy of opportunities, lack of books, lack of motivation, working conditions, not receiving education in the family before starting school. Below are the statements made by teachers named Ö4 and Ö5:

Ö4: "Well, I'm an idealist person. I try to do my best as much as possible, so I never do my profession as a teacher for money. When they say to me at the beginning of the year, they say, come and enter this class, we will not pay you for six months, I will not speak up. I will enter. At least my logic this is; I save one person. That one person saves two people, two people saves three people, whatever I can save. I teach, I seriously think about it. It's a lie, like stale food all the time, heat it up and throw it in front of you and you say if there is any improvement, so even yesterday, my teacher Arif came and liked the class, you know, you will say that you have been happy about this for 20 years, but when I think about the conditions here, your parents' reading level is very, very low. I find it successful when I think that most of them are not literate."

Ö5: "I see myself as a role model in values education. I think that my opportunities are limited. I don't think that the books are very sufficient either. In this way. Successful and unsuccessful, so frankly, when I look at it as a realist, I think I have deficiencies. I don't think I have much motivation in this regard. The reason is the working conditions. I don't have much motivation, I don't have the strength for it, frankly, but I think that values education is also a very important issue. I can't flatter myself like that, so now I have some deficiencies."

Findings Obtained from Observation of Teachers' Lessons

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Two teachers' Life Science lectures were observed. These teachers are teachers named Ö1 and Ö2. The data obtained from the lectures are as follows:

Data obtained from the Life Studies course of teacher named Ö1:

Table 16. Teaching Process

Titles	Explanation
Lesson	Life science
Subject	Leader Ataturk
Class	3rd Class
Root values mentioned in the lesson	Patriotism, patience, love, self-control, honesty, justice, respect, responsibility, helpfulness
Values covered in the lesson	Courage, fearlessness, not losing hope, being faithful, not giving up, planning, regularity, hard work, love of nation, leadership, innovation, struggle
Methods, techniques and activities used in root value or value teaching	Lecturing, question-answer, reading and interpreting poetry, inferring meaning, giving examples, associating with experiences

Evaluation activities used Q&A, homework
in root value or value
teaching

How was the content processed in root value or value teaching? The content determined in the curriculum and in the book was complied with, but there were also some exceptions during the course teaching process. As an example, the use of poetry that is not included in the book can be shown.

How was the book used in root value or value teaching? The lecture sequence in the book was followed, but the parts of the book that were not mentioned were also mentioned. As an example, students can be shown to use questions that are not included in the book.

The reasons why the root values or values cannot be acquired by the students Including undesirable behaviors in the classroom, not focusing enough attention on the lesson, not using activities in which students will be active enough.

Data obtained from the Life Studies course of teacher named Ö2:

Table 17. Teaching Process

Titles	Explanation
Lesson	Life science
Subject	Emergency Numbers
Class	2. Class
Root values mentioned in the lesson	Responsibility, respect
Values covered in the lesson	-
Methods, techniques and activities used in root value or value teaching	Lecture, question and answer, brainstorming, case study
Evaluation activities used in root value or value teaching	writing work
How was the content processed in root value or value teaching?	The content determined in the curriculum and in the book was complied with, but there were also some exceptions during the course teaching process. An example can be given to include an example event.

How was the book used in root value or value teaching?	The lecture order in the book was followed, but not all of the works in the book were mentioned.
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The reasons why the root values or values cannot be acquired by the students	Including undesirable behaviors in the classroom, not focusing enough attention on the lesson, not using activities in which students will be active enough.
--	--

Conclusion

In this part of the study, conclusions were drawn from the data obtained and interpretations were given regarding the results.

In the third question asked to the teachers in the semi-structured interview form, they were asked to say what the concept of value evokes. Teachers gave the most important answer (3 people) and morality (2 people). Based on these data, it is seen that the concept of value is correctly structured in the minds of teachers. In addition, the concept that makes our life easier (1 person) and learning to learn (1 person) given by the teachers show that the answer is not structured in only one dimension in the minds of the teachers.

In the semi-structured interview form, the fourth question asked to the teachers was the questions about the values that should be taught to the students, and the most answers were love (6 people), respect (5 people), tolerance (3 people). Teachers gave 12 different answers to this question and 23 in total. These answers are not sufficient in number because when it is thought that there are ten root values and many values are included in the program, both related to and outside the root values, it is seen that the teachers do not have enough knowledge of the values. The answers given by the teachers, knowing how to speak and expressing themselves (1 person) and self-directedness (1 person), show that the teachers do not understand the meaning of the concept of value shallowly and in a single pattern.

In the semi-structured interview form, the question asked as the fifth question, what is the meaning of the root value for you, was mostly answered by the teachers as no answer (2 people). Based on this answer and the other answers given by the teachers, we see that the teachers do not have knowledge about the meaning of the root value concept specified in the program.

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In the semi-structured interview form, the sixth question asked to the teachers as the sixth question, what are the root values, was answered by the teachers mostly as respect (6 people), love (5 people), tolerance (3 people), rules (3 people), honesty (2 people). From the answers given by the teachers, it is seen that the values of love, respect, honesty and helpfulness are the values expressed in the program. Although the teachers did not know the meaning of the root value in the fifth question, they mentioned four root values in the sixth question, indicating that they used the root values even though they did not know the meaning of the root value. Although there are 10 root values in total, the fact that the teachers mentioned 4 root values shows that the teachers do not have sufficient knowledge about the content of the root values.

In the semi-structured interview form, the seventh question asked to the teachers was the question "What other values would you add to the root values?" Mostly, the teachers gave the answer of respect (6 people), empathy (2 people), valuing people (2 people), valuing animals (2 people). Among the answers given by the teachers, the values of respect and love are among the root values. This situation shows that teachers do not have enough knowledge about root values. Different from the root values, the teachers suggested different root values such as tolerance, catching up with the pace of society, modernity, spiritual values, Islam, freedom, environmental awareness, and being human. This shows that teachers can look at values from different perspectives. Teachers made 13 different value propositions and a total of 23 value propositions. This situation shows that teachers do not have enough knowledge about values.

In the semi-structured interview form, the eighth question asked to the teachers was the most empathy (3 people), drama (2 people), learning by doing (2 people), parent interviews, to the question of which methods, techniques or activities are used in teaching the root values or values. (2 people), question-answer (2 people). It is seen from the answers given by the teachers to the question that they used 14 different methods, techniques or activities and a total of 20 methods, techniques or activities. This situation shows that teachers do not use enough methods, techniques or activities or they do not have enough information about the methods, techniques or activities used in teaching root values or values.

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In the semi-structured interview form, the ninth question asked to the teachers was the question of which evaluation activities are used in the teaching of the root values or values, and mostly observation (4 people), question-answer (2 people) answers were given by the teachers. Teachers said that they used 9 different evaluation activities and 13 evaluation activities in total. This situation shows that the teachers do not use enough assessment activities to evaluate whether the root values or values are acquired or they do not have enough knowledge about assessment activities.

In the semi-structured interview form, the tenth question asked to the teachers was whether the content of the Life Sciences course is sufficient for gaining the core values or values, and 4 of the teachers expressed the opinion that it was not enough and 2 of them were sufficient. Based on this situation, it is seen that teachers generally think that the content of the Life Studies course is not sufficient. This situation shows that teachers are not satisfied with the content of the Life Studies course.

When asked as the eleventh question to the teachers in the semi-structured interview form, to the question of whether the Life Studies textbook is sufficient for gaining the root values or values, all of the teachers answered that it is not sufficient. Based on this situation, it is seen that the teachers think that the Life Studies textbook is not sufficient. This situation shows that teachers are not satisfied with the Life Studies textbook.

When asked as the twelfth question to the teachers in the semi-structured interview form, 5 of the teachers stated that they won and 1 of them could not. This situation shows that most of the students learn the correct value and can internalize the desired value in root value or value teaching.

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The thirteenth question in the semi-structured interview form was asked to the teachers, and mostly family (5 people), environment (3 people), role models (2 people) were given by the teachers to the question of what are the reasons for the students not gaining root values or values. This situation shows that the biggest problem in the failure of teachers to gain root values or values is the family and how important the family is for teachers in education. In addition, it is seen that the environment in which the student lives and the people he takes as an example are perceived as an important element in education for teachers. The fact that the answers given by the teachers are close to each other shows that the teachers have similar problems.

In the semi-structured interview form, the fourteenth question asked to the teachers was the answer to the question of who has a role in the process of students gaining root values or values, mostly family (6 people), environment (6 people), teacher (3 people), school (2 people). . Based on these answers, teachers generally emphasized the importance of the family, themselves, the school and the environment in the teaching of root values or values. It is seen that teachers express that they do not have a duty to teach fundamental values or values only to the school or to themselves, and that they express that success can come by supporting this teaching in out-of-school environments.

When asked as the fifteenth question in the semi-structured interview form, how do you evaluate yourself in the teaching of root values or values, 3 people said that they had deficiencies and 3 people said that they were successful. These answers show that teachers mostly do not see themselves as faultless or perfect, they know that they have deficiencies during teaching and they make efforts to compensate for these deficiencies. This situation shows that teachers do not act biased when evaluating themselves.

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According to the data obtained from the observation results of the teachers' Life Science lessons, it is seen that the teachers did not have any problems in conveying the root values or values related to the subject, but that the root values or values related to the subject were not conveyed at all. It is seen that the teachers do not give enough space to the activities in which the students will be active in the teaching of root values or values. As an evaluation activity, it is seen that the studies in which the student can be more active are not included in the same way. This situation shows that teachers do not have enough knowledge about methods, techniques or activities or they do not include activities in which students can be more active in their lessons. The teachers acted in accordance with the content and the book, but sometimes they included parts that were not included in the content and the book. This shows that teachers do not see the content and the book as sufficient for teaching. The undesirable behaviors of the students during the lesson and the inability of the students to be active enough during the lesson can be shown among the reasons why the root values or values cannot be acquired at the desired level.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results obtained from the research, some suggestions were made. These recommendations are:

Informative and instructive trainings can be given to teachers about the Life Studies curriculum.

Various trainings can be given to teachers regarding the methods, techniques or activities used in teaching root values or values.

Various trainings can be given to teachers regarding the evaluation activities that teachers apply as a result of teaching root values or values.

Necessary corrections can be made regarding the content of the Life Sciences book.

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Studies can be done to make the Life Studies textbook more equipped.

Additional studies or different studies can be provided by the teachers for the students who cannot gain the root values or values at the desired level.

Parent seminars can be organized to inform parents about root value or value teaching.

Opportunities can be created that will allow teachers to improve themselves in the subjects they deem themselves lacking.

It is possible to compare the results obtained by ensuring that the research is conducted with a larger number of people and in the same or different regions.

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